

D 5.1 PDEC

Plan for Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (PDEC) Activities, including Project brand and communication products. The PDEC will support the strategic and effective communication, dissemination, and exploitation of NETTAG+'s results and findings to all stakeholders including the media and general public, while managing IP protection.

Document Information

Grant Agreement no. 101112812

Call ID	HORIZON-MISS-2022-OCEAN-01
Project Name	Preventing, Avoiding and Mitigating Environmental Impacts of Fishing Gears and Associated Marine Litter
Project Acronym	NETTAG+
Project Website	
Deliverable ID	D5.1
Work Package Reference	WP5
Due Date of Deliverable	31/10/2023
Submission Date	18/10/2023
Dissemination Level	Public
Lead Partner	ERINN
Participating Partners	WWFMed / CIIMAR

Quality information and Revision History

Version	Authors	Date
1	Rebecca Pflanz, Marieke Reuver	05/10/2023

Summary NETTAG+ Project

NETTAG+ aims to provide a portfolio of three innovative smart and sustainable solutions to address the negative impacts of abandoned, lost or otherwise discarded fishing gear (ALDFG) on marine life and habitats. NETTAG+ will be based on synergistic activities between the fisheries industry, scientists and NGOs to develop three solutions to PREVENT, AVOID and MITIGATE the harmful impacts of ALDFG.

NETTAG+ will PREVENT marine litter derived from fisheries activities, AVOID loss of fishing gears, and MITIGATE harmful impact by removing existing ALDFG. These three solutions will jointly contribute to reduce ALDFG and marine pollution, namely by: reducing the introduction of hazardous chemicals and microplastics originating from ALDFG; reducing ghost fishing, bycatch and entanglements of sensitive or endangered species on ALDFG; and improving mapping, tracking and recovery technologies to retrieve ALDFG.

NETTAG+ aims to upgrade and upscale the integrative preventive approach that started in the previous NetTag project, and aims to replicate it in Mediterranean regions, providing the fisheries industry with three smart and environmentally-friendly solutions to reduce ALDFG and prevent the environmental impacts of fishing gears. The three solutions will be developed to maturity (TRL 7-8) by the end of the project, and will be tested, validated and demonstrated in real conditions in Atlantic and Mediterranean countries, namely Portugal (PT), United Kingdom (UK), Spain (SP), Italy (IT), Croatia (HR) and Malta (MT). NETTAG+'s ambition is to change the paradigm of the fisheries industry, aspiring to transform the societal perspectives about the role of fishers as Guardians and Cleaners of the Ocean. NETTAG+ will empower the sector to take effective actions to address marine pollution, promoting their role as key actors to tackle marine pollution.

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Executive Summary

The NETTAG+ Plan for Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (PDEC) outlines the EC rights and obligations of the consortium for dissemination, exploitation and communication (DEC) of the project results. It adopts EC best practice guidelines and defines the objectives of NETTAG+ DEC. It also identifies target stakeholders, proposes communication tools and channels, and outlines responsibilities and resources to carry out effective knowledge management, and to measure the impact.

All project participants have an obligation to participate in the DEC of NETTAG+ results and outputs to create impact, especially in their own countries and in their own communities. Within the PDEC, the DEC activities to be performed are described, along with protocols and processes to be followed.

NETTAG+ has two work packages dedicated to these activities (WP5 led by ERINN and WP6 led by WWF Med) specifically designed to support project communication and targeted dissemination activities to a wide audience (WP6) and facilitate the exploitation and innovation potential of the results to specific stakeholders (WP5). To support participants in DEC of results, a portfolio of resources will be developed under WP6. This portfolio will be updated regularly, and additional resources made available as required. NETTAG+ will make use of the latest tools and communication channels to ensure cost-effectiveness and maximum impact.

The PDEC has been developed by ERINN Innovation, who will assist in overseeing its continuous implementation together with WWF Med and CIIMAR. This is the first version of the PDEC and as it is a dynamic document, it will be evaluated at EC reporting stages and adjusted if needed.

1. Introduction

NETTAG+ aims at addressing the negative impacts of abandoned, lost or otherwise discarded fishing gears on marine life and habitats by providing a portfolio of three innovative and sustainable solutions to PREVENT, AVOID and MITIGATE the harmful impact of fishing gears. 1) The PREVENT objective focuses on empowering the fisheries sector as “guardians and cleaners of the Ocean”, by adopting more environmentally friendly fishing methods through awareness raising actions aimed at promoting more responsible fishing-related waste management practices. 2) The AVOID objective involves upscaling and improving an acoustic fishing gear localisation system - developed in the previous Nettag project - using low-cost transponders and surface locators and maximising its cost-effectiveness. 3) the MITIGATE objective focuses on developing robotic tools and advanced techniques to detect and remove abandoned fishing gear.

NETTAG+ builds upon the previous NetTag project and aims to replicate and maximise its approach across the Mediterranean region. The project will develop and test the solutions in Atlantic and Mediterranean countries, such as Portugal, the United Kingdom, Spain, Italy, Croatia, and Malta. To guarantee the adoption of NETTAG+ solutions, support the uptake and maximise the impact and long-term sustainability of NETTAG+, the project has put in place effective communication, dissemination, engagement and knowledge transfer (KT) strategies in two standalone work packages (WP5 ‘Exploitation & Innovation Potential’ and WP6 ‘Dissemination & Communication’).

1.1 Rationale

The NETTAG+ PDEC outlines the DEC strategies to be implemented by the consortium throughout the three- year project lifetime and beyond.

Adopting the EC’s best practice guidelines and aligning with rights and obligations outlined in the NETTAG+ Grant Agreement (GA) related to dissemination and exploitation, the PDEC describes internal processes and protocols set up to support communication, manage generated knowledge and to ensure exploitation of the NETTAG+ results. It identifies key project stakeholders, communication tools and channels and describes the means (tools, messages) of dissemination and measures to support exploitation.

1.2 Objectives

The PDEC aims to:

- Support the strategic and effective communication, dissemination, and exploitation of NETTAG+'s results and findings to all stakeholders including the media and general public;
- Provide a useful guide to all consortium members about rules and responsibilities surrounding DEC;
- Identify and profile the target audience for the different project results;
- Define the most effective dissemination, exploitation and communication channels, tools and actions tailored to relevant stakeholders;
- Outline knowledge management and transfer principles and protocols to ensure effective transfer and exploitation of Key Exploitable Results (KERs).
- Maximise post-project uptake by supporting consortia members to transfer results, defining impact pathways and validating transfer strategies that clearly outline the potential users and applications of the project's KERs and the Knowledge Transfer (KT) activity to ensure objective, measurable project outcomes and impacts.

To review the effectiveness of the strategy and measure the extent to which it is meeting the objectives, the PDEC will be evaluated and updated at regular intervals throughout the project (M18, M36). Exploitation measures will address the full range of potential users and focus on the efficient integration of new knowledge.

2. Key Principles Guiding the PDEC

2.1 Definitions and Terminology

The foundation of the NETTAG+ PDEC is the knowledge management process which has been implemented from the start of the project and which informs communication, dissemination, and exploitation (KT), in line with the European Commission (EC) definitions as follows:

- **Communication** is a strategically planned process that starts at the outset of the project and continues throughout its entire lifetime. It is aimed at promoting NETTAG+ and its results. It requires strategic and targeted measures for communicating about NETTAG+ and the project's results to a multitude of audiences, including policymakers, industry representatives and society, and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange. Activities used for communication purposes are, for example, a public website, press releases, feature articles, videos and social media.
- **Dissemination** is the public disclosure of the project results by any appropriate means (other than resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including open-access scientific publications in any medium. It

makes research results known to various stakeholder groups in a targeted way, enabling them to use the results in their own work. Further activities used for dissemination purposes are, for example, conferences, public outreach activities linked with TREC expeditions in the form of port calls along the EU coastline and collaboration with other EU-funded projects.

- **KT and exploitation of results** is more advanced than communication and dissemination, it involves the use of results in further research activities other than those covered by the project, or in developing, creating and marketing a product or process, or in creating and providing a service, or in standardisation activities, or feeding back into policymaking activities. It requires several steps including identifying exploitation mechanisms and activities, focused on identified end users to ensure impact and uptake of the results, which will provide measurable impacts for NETTAG+, while ensuring any project-generated IP is properly managed.

2.2 Rights, Rules and Obligations related to Results

This section outlines a summary of some key aspects of the rights and obligations relating to NETTAG+ results; however, it is not an exhaustive summary. For further details on the project and Horizon Europe rules surrounding issues such as ownership and protection of results please refer to the Grant Agreement (GA), Consortium Agreement (CA) and on specific rules for data outputs, please see D1.2 Data Management Plan (DMP; due in M6 and to be reviewed and updated in M18 and M33).

2.2.1 Ownership of Results

Results are owned by the participant that generates them. Two or more project participants' own results jointly if they have jointly generated them and it is not possible to establish the respective contribution of each participant or separate them, for the purpose of applying for, obtaining, or maintaining their protection (GA Article 16 – Annex 5). The joint owners must agree (in writing) on the allocation and terms of exercise of their joint ownership (joint ownership agreement), to ensure compliance with their obligations under the Grant Agreement. Unless otherwise agreed in the Consortium Agreement, each joint owner may grant non-exclusive licences to third parties to exploit the jointly-owned results (without any right to sub-license), if the other joint owners are given: at least 45 days advance notice and fair and reasonable compensation.

2.2.2 Protection of Results

Project partners which have received funding under the grant must adequately protect their results — for an appropriate period and with appropriate territorial coverage — if protection is possible and justified, taking into account all relevant considerations, including the prospects for commercial exploitation, the legitimate interests of the other project participants and any other legitimate interests.

2.2.3 Exploitation of Results

Project partners which have received funding under the grant must — up to four years after the end of the action — use their best efforts to exploit their results directly or to have them exploited indirectly by another entity, in particular through transfer or licensing.

If, despite a beneficiary's best efforts, the results are not exploited within one year after the end of the action, the beneficiaries must (unless otherwise agreed in writing with the granting authority) use the Horizon Results Platform to find interested parties to exploit the results. If results are incorporated in a standard, the beneficiaries must (unless otherwise agreed with the granting authority or unless it is impossible) ask the standardisation body to include the funding statement (see GA Article 17) in (information related to) the standard.

Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) & Management

NETTAG+ will follow the rules for IP set out and regulated by the EC. More information can be found in GA (Article 16.4) "Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) — Background and Results — Access Rights and Rights of Use". Each partner is responsible for adequately protecting their results if protection is possible and justified, taking into account all relevant considerations, including the prospects for commercial exploitation, the legitimate interest of other partners and any other legitimate interests.

To support IPR protection, NDAs will be put in place. In addition, this PDEC provides an IP checklist, which is attached in Annex 2. This will be implemented as part of the prior notice process for publications and data whereby publishing partners are asked to confirm that there is nothing exploitable in their publication nor data. Partners who are owners of results are asked to ensure that adequate steps towards protection are taken prior to D&E&C, by engaging actively with their allocated Technology Transfer officers, preventing unapproved disclosure of results. A "Results Ownership List" (ROL) will be reported as part of the final EC report.

Background And Access Rights To Background

NETTAG+ will follow the background rules set out and regulated by the NETTAG+ Consortium Agreement, which includes the identification of the background needed for implementing NETTAG+ or for exploiting its results. 'Background' means any data, know-how or information — whatever its form or nature (tangible or intangible), including any rights such as intellectual property rights — that is: (a) held by the beneficiaries before they acceded to the Agreement and (b) needed to implement the action or exploit the results. Specific limitations and/or conditions around each identified background are mentioned in Attachment 1 of the Consortium Agreement.

As the NETTAG+ Project builds on the results achieved from the prior NetTag Project, the background is relevant in this case. Within NETTAG+, the background brought into the project is listed in the Consortium Agreement (CA), Attachment 1. In the CA, parties have identified and agreed on the background for the project and have, where relevant, informed each other that access to specific Background is subject to legal restrictions or limits. Anything not listed in the CA (Attachment 1) shall not be the object of access right obligations regarding background.

2.2.4 Communication and Dissemination of Results

Each participant must disseminate their results as soon as feasible by disclosing them to the public (GA, Article 17). However, no dissemination may take place before a decision is made regarding possible protection (section 3.1). Other participants may object if their legitimate interests in relation to their results or background could potentially suffer harm.

Project participants that intend to disseminate their results must give at least 15 calendar days prior notice (see section 3.1.1) to other project participants (unless agreed otherwise), together with sufficient information on the results they will disseminate (GA Article 17 – Annex 5).

Any other participant may object within (unless agreed otherwise) 15 days of receiving notification if it can show that its legitimate interests in relation to the results or background would be significantly harmed. In such cases, the results may not be disseminated unless appropriate steps are taken to safeguard those interests.

Notwithstanding the above, certain communication and dissemination activities which, by their nature, must be carried out in a timely manner (e.g. social media posts, promotional articles and reports) will be exempt from the obligation to give prior notice to all project participants so as not to impede the project's communications & dissemination strategy, provided that all NETTAG+ project participants engaged in such action are in agreement, and provided that the duty of confidentiality is respected (GA Article 13).

Open Science and Open Access to Scientific Publications

Open Science (or Open Research) describes the transparent and collaborative approach to the scientific process based on open cooperative work, tools and diffusion of knowledge. This section outlines OA requirements for peer-reviewed scientific publications. For more information on open science in relation to research data and FAIR principles, please see the NETTAG+ Data Management Plan (D1.2 - DMP).

Providing OA to peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to results of Horizon Europe funded projects is an obligation for all grants. All project participants must ensure OA to peer-reviewed scientific publications relating

to their results (GA Article 17 – Annex 5). The collection and upload of these publications and their underlying digital research data to an open access repository is the responsibility of the publication authors/data owners.

Participants are encouraged to provide open access to ALL publications, even if they are not peer-reviewed.

In relation to **Open Access to scientific publications**, all project participants must ensure that:

- at the latest at the time of publication, a machine-readable electronic copy of the published version or final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication is deposited in a trusted repository for scientific publications.
- And, at the same time, give information about any research output, or any other tools and instruments, that would be needed to validate the conclusion of the scientific publication, via the (same) repository.
- Immediate open access is provided to the deposited publication via the repository, under the latest available version of the Creative Commons Attribution International Public Licence (CC BY) or a licence with equivalent rights; for monographs and other long-text formats, the licence may exclude commercial uses and derivative works (e.g. CC BY-NC, CC BY-ND)

Beneficiaries (or authors) must retain sufficient intellectual property rights to comply with the open access requirements.

Metadata of deposited publications must be open under a Creative Common Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or equivalent, in line with the FAIR principles (in particular machine actionable) and provide information at least about the following: publication (author(s), title, date of publication, publication venue); Horizon Europe or Euratom funding; grant project name, acronym and number; licensing terms; persistent identifiers for the publication, the authors involved in the action and, if possible, for their organisations and the grant. Where applicable, the metadata must include persistent identifiers for any research output or any other tools and instruments needed to validate the conclusions of the publication.

How to provide open access:

Beneficiaries/authors may publish in the venue of their choice, either in a closed venue (i.e. access to all content is restricted), an open access publishing venue or in a hybrid publishing venue, provided that all their open access-related obligations as detailed in this section are complied with:

- Open access publishing venues — Are publishing venues whose entire scholarly content is published in open access (e.g. open access journals, books, publishing platforms, repositories or preprint servers).

- **Hybrid publishing venues** — Are publishing venues which provide part of their scholarly content in open access, while another part is accessible through subscriptions/payments (e.g. hybrid journals and books). These are often journals/books based on subscription/purchase which provide open access to part of their content when an open access fee is paid by their authors/institutions (paid ad hoc or on the basis of an institutional agreement with the publishers).
- **Mirror and sister journals** (i.e. more recently established open access versions of existing subscription journals, which may share the same editorial board as the original journal and usually have (at least initially) the same or very similar aims, scope and peer review processes and policies; these journals often have a name similar to the subscription title but a different ISSN) are considered open access publishing venues for Horizon Europe grants (not hybrid journals).

In parallel, beneficiaries/authors must deposit their publication in a machine-readable format (i.e. structured format that can automatically be read and processed by a computer) in a trusted repository — before or at publication time — and immediately provide open access to the publication through that repository.

 Publishing in an open access venue without depositing in a repository, does NOT comply with the open access requirements. All peer-reviewed publications must be deposited in trusted repositories and open access provided to them through the repositories.

In Horizon Europe, only publication fees in full open access venues for peer-reviewed scientific publications are eligible for reimbursement.

When choosing the publishing venue and the repository, beneficiaries/authors must keep in mind that licensing requirements, metadata requirements and validation requirements must also be complied with at this time.

 The European Commission offers Horizon Europe beneficiaries [Open Research Europe \(ORE\)](#), an **open access publishing platform with no publishing fees**. ORE is offered as an additional publishing option to Horizon Europe beneficiaries. When ORE is the selected publishing venue, all requirements for open access to scientific publications are automatically fulfilled, as ORE deposits publications in the all-purpose repository [Zenodo under the conditions required by Horizon Europe](#).

Immediate open access through the repository must be provided either to the final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication or to the final published peer-reviewed version. Please also note that publication fees are only eligible when publishing in full open access publishing venues (venues in which the entire scholarly content is openly accessible to all) and not in hybrid venues. Publication fees may, in particular, include peer review fees,

including where the peer review service has been provided by an organisation different from the one providing the publishing venue. Peer review fees for publications are eligible for reimbursement only for the first round of peer reviewers.

Open science: research data management

In addition to the above, participants must manage the digital research data generated in the action ('data') responsibly, in line with the FAIR principles. See all details in the NETTAG+ data management plan (DMP – D1.2)

For more information on OA, please consult GA Article 17 - Annex 5 (Communication, Dissemination, Open Science and Visibility) and the associated AGA additional sections.

2.2.5 Visibility of funding

Communication and dissemination activities related to the project, and any infrastructure, equipment, vehicles, supplies or major result funded by the grant must acknowledge EU support and display the European flag (emblem) and funding statement (GA Article 17.2). This includes media relations, conferences, seminars, information material, such as brochures, leaflets, posters, presentations, etc., in electronic form, via traditional or social media, etc., dissemination activities and any infrastructure, equipment, vehicles, supplies or major result funded by the grant. When displayed in association with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence. For the purposes of their obligations under this Article, the project participants may use the EU emblem without first obtaining approval from the Agency. This does not, however, give them the right to exclusive use. Moreover, they may not appropriate the EU emblem or any similar trademark or logo, either by registration or by any other means.

Any communication or dissemination activity related to the project must include the following EU emblem and funding acknowledgement:

Funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe Program, Grant Agreement No. 101112812 (NETTAG+). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Any communication or dissemination activity related to the project in which non-EU funded participants are involved must include the emblem and acknowledgement above, as well as the following non-EU funding emblems and acknowledgements where relevant:

UK Partners on NETTAG+ are supported by UKRI under the UK Government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee Grant No. 10066822 (University of Newcastle Upon Tyne), (Succorfish Ltd.)

When displayed in association with these non-EU funding emblems and acknowledgements, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence.

The EU and UKRI funding emblems and acknowledgements are available on the project's [Google Drive folder](#).

2.3 General Data Protection Regulation Implications

The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) (EU 2016/679) provides enhanced protection to individuals' data privacy rights. Organisations storing or using personal data (anything that allows identification of an individual) must clearly disclose what data is being collected and how, why it is being processed/used, how long it is being retained, and if it is being shared with any third parties. Personal data can be names, email addresses, job titles, phone numbers, and anything that allows identification of an individual.

2.3.1 GDPR Compliance (website, mailing list and events)

NETTAG+ conforms with Horizon Europe ethical guidelines, including "Data protection and privacy ethics guidelines" and the "Guidance for Applicants on Informed Consent", these are addressed in detail in the corresponding ethics, social and legal aspects plan which will be developed at the early stages of the proposal by CIIMAR and will be available to all projects' members (T1.3) to raise awareness and foresee in detail which project tasks and activities need to consider self-ethical regulations. Through this protocol, the project's members will be informed and briefed about the ethical requirements of the project in conducting, progressing and completing its activities.

From the start of the project, all technological tools that will collect personal data will follow the anonymous personal data protection rules, as well as individual questionnaires that can be passed to the fisher or other communities will not collect individual personnel data and will follow the GDPR regulations. The NETTAG+ project website (managed by CIIMAR, WWFMed) will be fully compliant with GDPR by incorporating a Privacy Statement and Cookie Bar informing website visitors about what NETTAG+ does with any personal data gathered. The mailing list will only be used to share NETTAG+ related information and news. Photographs and videos taken at NETTAG+

project events, workshops, meetings and promotional activities will comply with GDPR through the use of consent forms to be signed by all persons involved.

3. Pre- and Post-Dissemination Requirements

3.1 Pre-Dissemination Requirements

3.1.1 Prior Notice Procedure

For all types of Publications, Dissemination and Communication Activities (including scientific publications, oral and poster presentations, non-scientific and non-peer reviewed publications, etc.) where **NETTAG+ results or outputs** are presented, a Prior Notice Procedure (protocol below) must be applied.

Participants involved in the dissemination of results from the NETTAG+ project (owned by one or several parties) must give **at least 15 days advance notice** to the other partners (unless agreed otherwise), together with sufficient information on the results it will disseminate (GA Article 17 – Annex 5). However, partners are encouraged to give **45 days advance notice**, as laid out in the Consortium Agreement (CA Article 8.4.2.1).

PROTOCOL – Prior Notice Procedure

- *Participant(s) proposing a dissemination activity (submission/communication/publication) should inform all project participants of their intent at least **15 calendar days** before submitting/communicating/publishing using the 'Prior Notice Email Template' below and upload/attach the planned submission/communication/publication (full draft, if possible, but at a minimum this must include an abstract including title, author(s), project participants involved and details on where it will be submitted/communicated/published and/or presented).*
- *Project participants have **15 calendar days** to object if they can show that their legitimate interests in relation to the submission/communication/publication would be significantly harmed if the disclosure is permitted. In such cases, the results may not be disseminated unless appropriate steps are taken to safeguard those interests.*
- *Any objection to the planned submission/communication/publication shall be made in accordance with the GA by written notice to the NETTAG+ Coordinator and to the participant(s) proposing the submission/communication/publication, within **15 calendar days** after receipt of the notice. Any objection needs to be justified and precise suggested modifications given. An objection is justified if:*
 1. *It adversely affects protection of results/background of the objecting party.*
 2. *Legitimate interests of the objecting party would be significantly harmed.*
 3. *The proposed publication includes Confidential Information of the objecting Party. (CA Article 8.4.2.2)*
- *If no objection is made within the above stated timeline, or if objections are addressed and accepted by the objecting participant(s), the submission/communication/publication is permitted.*

- *If an objection has been raised the involved Parties shall discuss how to overcome the justified grounds for the objection on a timely basis (for example by amendment to the planned publication and/or by protecting information before publication) and the objecting Party shall not unreasonably continue the opposition if appropriate measures are taken following the discussion.*

The objecting Party can request a publication delay of not more than 90 calendar days from the time it raises such an objection. After 90 calendar days the publication is permitted, provided that the objections of the objecting Party have been addressed. (CA Article 8.4.2.4)

Prior Notice Email Template:

Dear NETTAG+ colleagues,

We have prepared a [insert planned disclosure e.g., communication/publication/dataset] to be submitted to [insert communication/publication name/item /data repository name] / presented at [insert event name/location] on [insert date]. Please see the [insert document type/information] attached.

In accordance with the Grant Agreement, any NETTAG+ participant who intends to disseminate their results/deposit their datasets in an open access repository must give prior notice to other project participants, who are then provided 15 calendar days to object to the proposed activity. In exceptional circumstances where such an activity is planned unexpectedly in a shorter timeframe, notice to other project participants must be given as soon as possible.

Objections are justified if:

- a) The protection of the objecting Party's Results or Background would be adversely affected, or*
- b) The objecting Party's legitimate interests in relation to its Results or Background would be significantly harmed, or*
- c) The proposed dissemination activity/dataset includes Confidential Information of the objecting Party.*

Any objection must include a precise request for necessary modifications. Please submit justified objections, with precise modifications, to [main participant email], the project coordinators Sandra Ramos (ssramos@ciimar.up.pt) and Marisa Almeida (calmeida@ciimar.up.pt) within 15 days, so before [insert date].

If no objections are received within this, we assume that all parties agree with the dissemination of these results/dataset being placed in an open access repository.

3.1.2 Intellectual Property (IP) Assessment Form

As outlined in the Grant Agreement, an IP checklist will be implemented as part of the prior notice process, whereby participants who intend to disseminate results will be asked to confirm that there is nothing exploitable in relation to the results they intend to disseminate, to ensure no IP is accidentally exposed. Participants must send a completed IP Assessment Form to IB lead ERINN who will assess the form, with support from relevant WP leads where needed,

as outlined in the protocol below. The NETTAG+ IB will support IPR protection through assessing results, including their exploitation potential, as part of the knowledge management and transfer process.

PROTOCOL – IP Assessment Form

- *Participant(s) proposing a dissemination activity (submission/communication/publication) involving NETTAG+ results that haven't yet been disseminated previously, should send information on the intended activity to IB lead ERINN (marieke@erinn.eu) with the completed IP Assessment Form for the respective results (Appendix Annex 2). Timeline = latest **15 days** in advance of the intended dissemination activity.*
- *ERINN will review and communicate with the proposing participant(s) in case of necessary clarifications. The assessment consists of:*
 1. *Preliminary screening, i.e., checking if all information required from the participant is included in the IP Assessment Form;*
 2. *Reviewing of the activity (at least the abstract, but ideally the whole publication draft or similar) to identify potentially exploitable knowledge;*
 3. *Identification of potential conflicts of interest related to ownership, authorship and institutions involved, including entities or other projects.*
- *If any information is lacking or insufficient, ERINN will request further details from the proposing participant(s) and the assessment period will be suspended until the participant responds with adequate clarification.*
- *If ERINN indicates that the result(s) could (potentially) be considered commercially exploitable, the participant must carry out their best effort to protect and exploit the result and the planned activities should be postponed:*
 1. *In this case, firstly, ERINN will inform the proposing participant(s) about this situation and request that the relevant participant(s) (together with their technological transfer/IP legal officer(s)), confirm whether these results indeed are commercially exploitable and indicate whether there is an interest in exploiting such results, and how they want to proceed (each participant institution will have a disclosure of invention system).*
 2. *If it is deemed that the result is commercially exploitable, and if no IP exploitation is envisaged by the owner(s) of the results, it is best practice to consider offering to transfer it to other project participants or third parties better positioned for the exploitation of the results and willing to seek their protection. In such case, the project participants' or third parties must accept to protect the results by written consent within 10 days to all project participants.*
 3. *If such transfer is not done, project participants that have received European Union funding but do not intend to protect their results, must inform the European Commission (EC) NETTAG+ Project Officer before any dissemination activity is carried out – by means of informing the NETTAG+ Coordinator as only the Coordinator can directly contact the EC Project Officer. This notification is mandatory for up to four years after the end of the project.*
 4. *The EC may – under certain circumstances – assume ownership of the results, except in any of the following cases:*
 - *It is not possible, reasonable or justified to protect;*
 - *There is a lack of potential for commercial or industrial exploitation;*

→ The consortium participant intends to transfer the results to another participant, or third party established in an EU Member State or associated country that will protect them;
→ An extension of protection would not be justified given the circumstances. In the case that the EC will assume the ownership, the EC must formally notify the concerned participants within 15 days of receiving notification.

5. If owner(s) of the results, other project participants or third parties, and the EC do not assume the ownership and do not take the necessary measures to protect it, ERINN's assessment is complete with a recommendation in the IP Assessment Form. The IP Assessment Form is then signed by ERINN and sent to the proposing participant(s), with the Coordinator (ssramos@ciimar.up.pt; calmeida@ciimar.up.pt) in cc.

- If the intended dissemination or communication activity involving NETTAG+ results does not involve exploitable results, ERINN's assessment is complete once the recommendation(s) is/are included in the IP Assessment Form, and it is signed by ERINN.
- If there is any doubt on whether the result(s) could (potentially) be considered commercially exploitable, then ERINN will share the completed IP Assessment Form with the Innovation Board and ask them to support in the assessment (following the steps above).
- If no exploitable information is identified, all documents (including the completed IP Assessment Form) are sent to the proposing participant(s), with the Coordinator (ssramos@ciimar.up.pt; calmeida@ciimar.up.pt) in cc to inform them that they can go ahead with the intended dissemination activity (submission/communication/publication) as planned.

3.2 Post-Dissemination Requirements

As part of the EU contractual requirements, all Scientific Publications, Dissemination Activities and Communication Activities are reported as part of the Continuous Reporting of the project in the EC Funding and Tender Opportunities Portal (EC Portal).

3.2.1 Continuous Reporting of Scientific Publications

Scientific Publications must be uploaded to the EC Portal once they have been accepted for publication. This includes articles in journals, publications in conference proceedings/workshops, books/monographs, chapters in a book, thesis/dissertation, etc.

NOTE: Scientific Publications resulting from NETTAG+ will be collated and uploaded to the EC Portal by CIIMAR. Project participants do NOT need to upload this information to the Portal themselves. Participants are asked to send their publications to CIIMAR (ssramos@ciimar.up.pt; calmeida@ciimar.up.pt; nettag@ciimar.up.pt) as soon as available and no later than two weeks after the official publication date, see detailed Protocol in section 3.2.2 below.

3.2.2 Continuous Reporting of Dissemination Activities and Communication Activities

NOTE: All Dissemination Activities and Communication Activities will be centrally collated and uploaded to the EC Portal by WWF Med. Project participants do NOT need to upload this information to the EC Portal themselves. To successfully manage the recording of these activities, WWFMed requires all participants to routinely update the “NETTAG+ Continuous Reporting Log” which will be shared with all participants and located on the NETTAG+ Google Drive WP6 folder.

PROTOCOL – EC Reporting of Scientific Publications, Dissemination activities and Communication Activities

- 1. All project participants are required to keep track of all their Scientific Publications, Dissemination Activities and Communication Activities during project implementation.*
- 2. The “NETTAG+ Continuous Reporting Log” will be developed by WWFMed and CIIMAR to support with the reporting of these activities in the form of an Excel sheet. The Continuous Reporting Log will be shared with all project participants in the Google Drive.*
- 3. Project participants should regularly contribute the complete information to update the Log which contains separate worksheets to report on 1) Scientific Publications and 2) Dissemination Activities and 3) Communication Activities.*
- 4. The log will be reviewed by beneficiary WWFMed and CIIMAR for completeness and correctness at EC reporting stages.*

3.2.3 Patents (IPR) Reporting

NETTAG+ participants are responsible for tracking their Intellectual Property (IPR) resulting from the project. Whenever a new IPR has been filed (the EC recommends filing with the European Patent Office), participants are required to notify the coordinators (ssramos@ciimar.up.pt, calmeida@ciimar.up.pt) and ERINN (marieke@erinn.eu) with the relevant information. Project participants are responsible for uploading the required information in relation to their IPR directly to the EC Portal. Participants are required to provide the following details:

- Identification of IPR type and Confidentiality
- Type of IPR (Patent/Trademark/Registered Design/Utility Model/Other)
- Confidentiality (Yes/No)
- Application Title

- Embargo end date

3.2.4 Datasets

Information around and reporting requirements for NETTAG+ digital research datasets can be found in D1.2 Data Management Plan (DMP; due in M6).

3.2.5 Overview of Post-Dissemination Continuous Reporting Protocols

Item	Action needed by acting participant	Participant uploading to EC Portal
Scientific Publications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Send final Scientific Publications to CIIMAR • Confirm the OA repository where the published peer-reviewed scientific publication has been shared 	CIIMAR
Dissemination Activities and Communication Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Record all Dissemination activities and Communication activities in the 'NETTAG+ Communications and Dissemination Reporting Log' 	WWF Med
Patents (IPR)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Record and upload the required information to the EC Portal • Notify ERINN of new IPR filed 	Participant owning the IPR
Datasets	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Send updated/completed dataset inventory template to CIIMAR • Complete the dataset tab on the "NETTAG+ Continuous Reporting Log" 	CIIMAR

4. Stakeholder Engagement

The purpose of the engagement activities described in the NETTAG+ PDEC is to facilitate dialogue, build relationships and generate exchanges between NETTAG+ and relevant stakeholders as described below.

4.1 Internal Stakeholders - Project Bodies

Advisory Board (AB)

The Advisory Board (AB) of the project is composed by external experts from various organisms, European and International, public and private. The role of the Advisory Board will be to review annual reports, act as a sounding board to the project and provide access to their networks to reach out to relevant parties to maximise communication, dissemination and exploitation measures. The Advisory Board will meet with the Executive Board on an annual basis, or more frequently if needed.

NETTAG+'s Advisory Board rests upon the knowledge and experience of world-renowned experts in their respective fields:

- **Joel Baziuk**, Associate Director, Global Ghost Gear Initiative
- **José Moutinho**, AIRCentre and Coordinator of the BlueMissionAA
- **Rita Sá**, ANP | WWF Portugal and Coordinator of Participesca
- **Raul Garcia Rodriguez**, WWF Spain
- **Christopher Sweeting**, Senior Evidence Specialist at Marine Management Organisation
- **Michael Elliot**, professor University of Hull and Director of IECS Ltd
- **Emma Bello Gomez**, Executive Director of the EuroMarine Network
- **Leo Thompson**, Commercial Fisheries Manager Osted

Innovation Board (IB)

The Innovation Board (IB), consists of all WP leaders and external experts in the different project-relevant topics from the External Advisory Board as well as representatives from the industry (direct end users of many KERs) plus Executive Board members on call, depending on the type of KER. Additional relevant experts will be sought as required, particularly if end users not represented or identified by the consortium show an interest in the NETTAG+ solutions.

The Innovation Board will support exploitation and valorisation of NETTAG+ results. The IB is an advisory board, which will make recommendations on dissemination and exploitation, but all decisions will be made by partner(s) owning the results. ERINN and the Innovation Board will support KER owners in planning the implementation of KTPs (identifying relevant end users, supporting and advising on seeking projections for high potential KERs) and dissemination activities to support transfer. This customised approach will increase the likelihood that 1) KERs will be transferred and exploited successfully, and the results applied; 2) there is an increased potential for impact from the transfer; and 3) it is possible to measure and demonstrate the impact of the transfer.

4.2 Stakeholder Engagement Strategy

Likely end users of NETTAG+ KERs include:

- **Fishing Industry:** Fishers and fishers' representatives (APMSHM; ARVI; CoGePa; MAFA) from 5 countries (Portugal, Spain, Italy, Croatia, Malta), fishing gear manufacturers (C&S), Fishing port authorities, Maritime technology companies.

- **Recycling companies:** Companies working on integrated approaches for managing plastic resources and upcycling/recycling them such as Waste Free Oceans (WFO), 4Ocean, Marine Litter Solutions, Plastix.
- **Policy-makers:** local/national/regional/EU policy-makers on fisheries (e.g fisheries ministries; EU DG MARE, EMSA); marine Litter/Circular economy (e.g. infrastructure and environment ministries and local administrative departments); environmental conservation (environment/ocean ministries, MPA managers)
- **Governmental administrations:** Such as government-led environmental protection agencies (EPA).
- **Marine litter Initiatives and platforms:** GGGI, VGMFG, MEDSEALITTER, UN Global Partnership on Marine Litter including the UNEP digital platform, EEA Marine Litter Watch, EMODnet Marine Litter.
- **Environmental NGOs:** NGOs involved in marine conservation and protection. Provider countries, CNA, database operators, lawyers, and environmental managers.
- **Scientific Community:** data scientists and researchers exploring marine litter, plastics and Circular Economy as well as the harmful impacts of fishing gear; and also on acoustics, marine robotics. This target group also includes scientists in the field of exploring synergies between the fisheries sector and scientists and fish health professionals/companies.
- **Civil Society:** Coastal communities especially those living in the project sites, the general public, media. The project also indirectly plays a role for this target group due to its long-term impact on reducing the negative impacts of ALDFG, preventing and reducing ocean pollution and reducing the ecological footprint of fisheries.

The NETTAG+ Stakeholder Engagement Strategy is outlined below in Table 1. It includes the objectives, activities and expected impact of engagement per main target stakeholder group throughout the full project duration.

Table 1: NETTAG+ Stakeholder Engagement Strategy

Target Groups	Tools of Engagement	Expected Impact
Fishing Industry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Prevent: Raise awareness on the negative impacts on ocean and marine wildlife caused by ALDFG and other litter derived from fisheries (e.g. domestic litter produced onboard; operational litter), and the need to reduce consumption of energy and resources. ● Promote best practices on board (fishing vessels). ● Work directly with fishing Ports to increase/improve their facilities to receive litter collected by fishing boats including personal interviews with port managers. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Reduced marine litter derived from fisheries and, consequently the environmental impact of fishing gears. ● increased life-span of fishing gear minimising end-of-life waste and contributing to a decrease of ALDFG in the Ocean. ● Implementation of the EU Port Reception Facilities Directive ● Preserved marine fauna and reduction of accidental catches (mainly of Endangered, Threatened and Protected (ETP) species),

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Promotion/Reward of volunteer service provided by fishers that retrieve ALDFG and litter passively collected by nets. The reward program will be co-defined with fishers representatives in T2.4. ● <u>AVOID</u>: Increase understanding and engage fishers in testing technological solution to mark/tag fishing gears to help them retrieve gears in case of loss. ● Increase understanding of fishers and engage them in testing acoustic tags with a new service to detect marine mammals, serving as an early warning of the presence of ETP species and thus avoiding bycatch of these species. 	<p>including the harmful effects of ghost fishing gears.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Contribution to the implementation of the EU Marine Strategy Framework Directive.
Marine Litter Recycling companies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Promote best practices at land (ports) regarding waste management, to properly forward litter for treatment, including recycling. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Increased implementation of the EU Port Reception Facilities Directive. ● Improved policies and facilities to properly manage and monitor fishing litter, including recycling and circular economy activities. ● Creation of adequate conditions for litter reception and treatment at fishing ports, including through recycling and reuse.
Policy and Decision makers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Work with policymakers and deliver policy-relevant outputs, e.g. two policy briefs about regulations, norms, and plans on marine litter management at Ports and the results of the reward program aimed at voluntary collection and management of marine litter. ● Assessment of willingness of fisheries regulators and EU/Mediterranean policymakers about the needed measures to tackle marine litter through the development of specific and effective strategies to improve existing policies. ● Identification of key national and regional policy stakeholders and tools that could support and scale-up the development of NETTAG+ solutions. ● Organisation and participation in meetings and events with key policy-makers. ● Work on medium-term policies on the theme of marine debris mitigation supporting the adoption of best practices and new technologies. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Development of informed policy recommendations to prevent marine litter. ● Policy recommendations to define regulations, norms, and plans on marine litter management at Ports. ● Implementation of effective strategies to improve existing policies on marine litter. ● Implementation of medium-term policies aimed at marine debris mitigation through the adoption of best practices and new technologies.
Marine litter initiatives and platforms & environmental NGOs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● National Clean Ocean Day (large sea clean-up events planned in WP6) will remove litter, including ALDFG, from the Ocean and beaches in Croatia, Italy, Malta Portugal and Spain. ● Testing of environmental harmfulness of fishing gear, including ALDFG and new gear from plastic and recyclable materials in field surveys, and laboratory and in-situ experiments. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Improved scientific knowledge of how ALDFG can adsorb chemical and biological hazardous agents and release microplastics. ● Advancement of the state-of-the-art regarding the negative effects of ALDFG, contributing to improving and preserving marine habitats. ● NETTAG+ will act as an important contributor to the ongoing solutions to

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Capitalise on fishers’ willingness to prevent fishing gear loss and to help clean the ocean in line with prior global initiatives arising from FAO, the UNEP and the IMO such as the Global Ghost Gear Initiative and the GloLitter Partnerships Project. 	<p>tackle ALDFG, namely the IMO mandatory goal-based requirement for the marking of fishing gear, and other programmes dedicated to prevent and reduce marine litter.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> NETTAG+ will extend the geographical scale of the awareness actions to include also the Mediterranean (Italy, Croatia, Malta).
Scientific Community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Open access scientific publications on results not requiring IP protection. Participation in conferences, strategic networks, workshops, trade fairs, and site visits. New partnerships via industry relevant meetings / organisations. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improved resolution of acoustic imaging systems and improved acoustic tags developed. Improved scientific understanding of the harmfulness of ALDFG as contaminant sinks and microplastic sources. Improved scientific understanding of social data on fisheries stakeholders’ perception of marine litter impacts. Improved scientific knowledge of economic data on cost-benefit assessment of the use of NETTAG+ technologies. Transfer of knowledge Raise awareness of the project results.
Citizens and society as a whole	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> National Clean Up Day (large sea clean-up events planned in WP6) will remove litter, including ALDFG, from the Ocean and beaches in Croatia, Italy, Malta Portugal and Spain. Work with fishers and NGOs to deliver dedicated communication and awareness actions (with the public and school children) to highlight the need to stop polluting and rethink the use of plastic. The importance of fishers in retrieving ALDFG and their volunteering clean-up service will be emphasized through the Clean Ocean Day events (WP2, T2.4), virtual reality scenarios, hands-on-activities and videogames. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increased literacy and awareness across general public and youth in project countries, highlighting the importance of ALDFG. Increased citizens’ support for the timely and effective implementation of the Single Use Plastic Directive. Increased citizen support of fishers’ role as Guardians and Cleaners of the Ocean. NETTAG+ will extend the geographical scale of the awareness actions to include also the Mediterranean (Italy, Croatia, Malta). Increased citizens’ participation in NETTAG+ related activities.

4.3 NETTAG+ Specific Stakeholder Events

4.3.1 Target Group: Fishing Industry

4.3.1.1 Awareness Actions For Fishers

Using educational/awareness material produced in T2.1, each fishers’ association (APMSHM, ARVI, CoGePa) and governmental and NGO group working with fishers (MAFA, WWF) will deliver awareness actions to their fisheries stakeholders (e.g. small and large-scale fishers). A package of six awareness actions will be delivered in several different regions (2 in Portugal; 2 in Spain; 1 in Italy; 1 in Croatia; 1 in Malta):

- 1) **1 Educational Seminar** to raise awareness on the adverse environmental and socio-economic effects of marine litter and ALDFG, and

- 2) **5 participatory workshops** to co-create solutions to promote/implement best practices regarding waste management, including themes such as: what is considered marine litter; appropriate waste management practices on board and at land; which facilities are needed at ports to handle litter derived from fisheries, including ALDFG; how to implement more environmental-friendly fishing methods to avoid bycatch and reduce consumption of energy and raw materials; and fishers' perceptions to reduce ALDFG and marine litter.

Solutions will be identified through a SWOT analysis considering the specificities of each region's fishery and its size. Between 30-50 participant fishers will attend per region, resulting in a total of 210-350 participant fishers. Each associate fishing vessel will receive materials developed in T2.1 to help with the implementation of good practices. Fishers' willingness/openness to create their own marine litter platform or joining an existing platform will also be explored.

4.3.1.2 Personal Interviews With Port Authorities

To better understand the current and potential state of marine litter management, personal interviews will be conducted with managers of port authorities in 10-20 ports (2-4 in each country, incl. Croatia, Italy, Malta, Portugal and Spain).

With the distribution of a survey to identified port managers', we will collect information about their knowledge and needs about current waste management policies, processes and infrastructure; as well as the economic and social implications of improvement, the major obstacles and challenges, and the capacity and willingness to improve policies to properly manage and monitor fishing litter, including adopting a circular economy approach.

Additionally, managers' interest and feedback about creating incentives on the following will be discussed:

1. Fishing vessels to retrieve derelict fishing gear, collect other items of marine litter, and deliver it to port reception facilities. (This task includes the consideration of potential of legislative obstacles in some countries that may prohibit bringing marine litter on land to the port).
2. The delivery of waste in port reception facilities such as the non-special fee system; and
3. The harmonisation of marine litter management policies and processes across the study countries in line with existing EU and international conventions (e.g. as priorities identified in the UN Barcelona Convention amended Regional Plan on Marine Litter Management in the Mediterranean; Decision IG.25/9) adopted in 2021.

4.3.1.3 Personal Interviews With Representative Fishers

Personal interviews will be conducted with representative of fishers in Portugal, Spain, Italy, Croatia and Malta to explore issues, motivations, challenges and needs regarding marine litter collection. The results will be used to co-produce, in conjunction with key representatives from fishing communities, culturally relevant sets of **fishers' reward programs** and **3 generic virtual reality scenarios**. By using a pre and post empathy questionnaire, the virtual reality scenarios will depict:

- 1) The current reality of marine litter impacting fishing activities and marine ecosystems;
- 2) A future scenario of the marine litter problem based on a 'business as usual approach'; and
- 3) A future scenario of the marine litter problem based on solutions provided by the NETTAG+ project.

The Interviews will focus on: fishers' voluntary contributions to the management of marine litter; proposed reward programs; and potential improvements of existing marine litter policies and practices in fishing ports. The 3 virtual reality scenarios will be used as leverage points to explore the social acceptability of different levels of marine litter within the project countries and associated existing and potential future policy and management strategies. The results from this task will contribute to the co-production of culturally sensitive best practice reward programs for fishers' voluntary collection and management of marine litter in the project countries, and recommendations for the implementation of such strategies at a local, national and EU level. The task will also highlight the receptiveness of fisheries regulators and EU/Mediterranean policy-makers to tackle problems of marine litter through the development of specific and effective strategies to improve existing policies and practices. The information on best practice reward programs will be provided to local, national and EU policy-makers (T6.4).

4.3.1.4 Clean Ocean Day Event

A special event entitled Clean Ocean Day will be organised by the fishers' associations and other partners where fishers from five countries (PT, SP, IT, HR, MT) will, during 1 day, collect litter resulting from a standard fishing day, and sort it into litter produced on board (including domestic and operational litter), and litter passively collected by the fishing gear.

The resulting litter will be analysed and classified (e.g. plastic, iron, glass, other) to assess the quantity and type of litter produced by fishing vessels versus that retrieved from the ocean. This event will be organised at an emblematic day (e.g. World Ocean Day, 8th June, World Plastic Day 3 July or similar), to have high visibility and participation among the general public and fishing communities. Bags to store the litter will be delivered to participating fishers (10-20 fishing vessels from each country in a total of 50-100 fishing vessels). Educational materials produced in Task 2.1 will be made available for representatives of fisher associations to share among

their members. A total of 7 of such events will be organised: 2 in Portugal; 2 in Spain; 1 in Italy; 1 in Croatia; 1 in Malta.

4.3.2 Target Group: Civil Society

The whole public and the general media will be targeted with a special focus on young people and specialised media who would be more interested in new robotic and high-tech ideas. This will include:

1. The organisation of up to **five National Clean-Up Events** - one in each country - namely: Portugal (organised by CIIMAR&APMSHM), Spain (organised by ARVI), Italy (organised by WWF Italy), Croatia (organised by WWF Adria) and Malta (organised by MAFA) in the form of a large sea-clean up event, involving fishers, recreational divers, schools kids, and the general public in sea-bottom and beach clean-ups;
2. Participation in the **EU Long Night of Science** with experiments and presentations of the use of acoustic tags and other technology;
3. The organisation of **hands-on activities and talks for school students**, incl. schools in coastal communities;
4. The development of an **educational program for schoolchildren** (10–13 years old) that will include a video game developed to raise awareness about the problem of marine litter. As support material for teachers and educational managers, a didactic unit will be also developed. The approach will be participative, cooperative and practical. The groups of schoolchildren, guided by a team of scientific disseminators, will be able to understand the importance of the conservation of the Ocean in a fun and entertaining way.

4.3.3 Target Group: Scientists

All partners, especially CIIMAR, INESCTEC, USC, UNEW, IIED, ERINN will present the main findings of NETTAG+ research to the scientific community, also fostering cooperation and scientific dissemination of NETTAG+ new knowledge using the FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable) principles compatible with ongoing EU initiatives such as the European Marine Observation and Data Network (EMODnet) and the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). This will include:

1. Organisation of workshops for scientists;
2. Participation to scientific events and conference;
3. Publication and dissemination of articles in open access scientific papers;
4. Participation in Brokerage events between academia and business.

4.3.4 Target Group: Policy And Decision Makers

All partners will be engaged in advocacy actions and products that will support the timely and effective implementation of NETTAG+ solutions. This will include:

1. Identification of key national and regional policy stakeholders and tools that could support and scale-up the development of NETTAG+ solution;
2. Development and dissemination (via email, social media and face-to-face meetings) of briefings to present the ecological, environmental and socio-economic benefits of NETTAG+ solutions and the policy actions needed to support their implementation;
3. Organisation and participation in meetings and events with key policy-makers. We are going to work on medium term policies on the theme of marine debris mitigation through the adoption of best practices and new technologies.

5. Knowledge Management, Transfer and Exploitation of Results

5.1 Knowledge Management and Transfer Overview

The European Commission has identified the importance of improving knowledge transfer (KT) between public research institutions and third parties, including industry and civil society organisations, as one of ten key areas for action¹. NETTAG+ will employ a proven Knowledge Management and Knowledge Transfer (KMKT) methodology to effectively address this key aspect of facilitating project impact.

This methodology was originally developed in the FP7 MarineTT project (GA #244164), and further developed and applied by the H2020 COLUMBUS project (GA #652690 - www.columbusproject.eu). This methodology has been applied in many FP7, Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe funded projects such as SIMBA, ERGO, RevivED water, RES4BUILD, SEALIVE, BIOGEARS, SEArcularMINE, AQUAEXCEL, TechOceanS and WaterLANDS.

Knowledge Management (KM) is the process of identifying, capturing, organising, analysing, and storing knowledge to ensure its availability to be transferred effectively to specific and relevant users.

Knowledge Transfer (KT) is the process of creating, organising, capturing/sharing/distributing knowledge to ensure its availability for future users, focusing the research on the wider needs of society and industry². KT encompasses both commercial and non-commercial activities such as research collaborations, consultancy, licensing, spinoff/spinout creation, researcher mobility, and publications etc. KT aims to support mutually beneficial

¹ https://ec.europa.eu/invest-in-research/pdf/download_en/knowledge_transfe_07.pdf

² http://europa.eu/rapid/press-release_MEMO-07-127_en.htm?locale=en

collaborations between universities, businesses and the public sector. The ultimate end benefit of successful KT is the application and influence of knowledge on targeted communities with greater impact (short and long term) across academia, industry and society.

Project Outputs/Knowledge Outputs (KOs) are described as “a unit of knowledge or learning generated by or through research activity. It is not limited to de-novo or pioneering discoveries but may also include new methodologies/processes, adaptations, insights, alternative applications of prior know-how/knowledge” [Definition developed by AquaTT in the context of the COLUMBUS project]. Typically, such knowledge might be referenced as a small part of a published paper, potentially three to five years after the approach is pioneered in a research project.

Key Exploitable Results (KERs) within NETTAG+ are tangible or intangible outputs of the action, such as data, knowledge and information whatever their form or nature³ which is deemed to have **high potential to be exploited** – meaning to make use and derive benefits - downstream the value chain of a product, process or solution, or act as an important input to policy, further research or education.

The means by which KERs will be identified from KOs is described in this section, but it is important to note that NETTAG+ is not implying any sort of value judgement between KOs and KERs. Rather, the project is simply using this distinction to allow knowledge that is of the most direct impact to the project, or is most feasibly transferable by the project, to be prioritised when assigning resources for transfer. By focusing on identifying KERs and transferring them when they have been assessed as having potential application and impact, it is possible to fast-track them, providing a faster impact on target- and end-users external to the project.

End User(s) are the individual(s) who are identified as being in a position where they could feasibly apply a given unit of Knowledge (KO/KER) and by doing so create the desired eventual impact of that knowledge. The KO/KER may need to evolve in order to reach the end user.

Target User is an individual(s) (organisations should be avoided where possible as specificity is crucial), whose position makes them a potential stepping-stone needed for a KO/KER to progress towards an identified end user and eventual impact. Target users are individuals with a specific mandate or responsibilities relevant to the specific KO/KER being evaluated. Target users should not merely be potential users of knowledge but should be individuals whose application of the knowledge is likely to advance it down the Pathway to Impact.

³ <https://intellectual-property-helpdesk.ec.europa.eu/>

A **Knowledge Transfer Plan (KTP) / Pathway to Impact Plan** is an informed stepwise plan for achieving the identified eventual impact of any piece of knowledge, regardless of whether this impact is achievable in the short, medium or long term. In NETTAG+ these will be developed for all selected KERs. The KTP identifies the end user capable of producing the desired eventual impact and outlines a specific series of transfer activities to intermediate target users.

Eventual Impact is the ultimate end benefit of the application of the knowledge (KO/KER). It is defined as an overall enhanced situation, generally for society but it can also be research or industry-specific. Eventual impacts can be the adoption of new technologies, products or innovation identified and refined within the project, or a change in protocols.

The KMKT of NETTAG+ KERs is integrated into the project through WP5 and is based on regularly collecting KOs through structured templates and interviews with project participants responsible for developing the results. Collected results will be assessed by ERINN, with support of the Innovation Board Members, based on criteria related to their innovation capacity, relevance to the sector, and expected impact. Knowledge Transfer Plans (KTPs) or Impact Plans will be developed for individual or clusters of KERs assessed as being of high potential for contributing to the project's objectives. This customised approach will increase the likelihood that 1) KERs will be transferred and exploited successfully, and the result applied; 2) there is an increased potential for impact from the transfer; and 3) it is possible to measure and demonstrate the impact of the transfer.

ERINN will coordinate and collaborate with the Innovation Board and other NETTAG+ WPs to support the KT. All project participants will contribute to the project's KMKT activities by adhering to the protocols and assisting in the collection and analysis of KOs and the transfer of high-potential KERs to end users. Input from all WPs will inform knowledge exchanges with all end user groups and will be facilitated through the awareness actions (WP2), demonstration activities (WP3-4), direct interviews (WP2) and communication activities (WP6). Additional bilateral exploitation meetings (M34-M36), will be organised with end-users (for high potential KER clusters), with support from relevant Innovation Board members, to support KTP implementation. Direct contact with the fishers as established during the project will facilitate transfer to other fishers not directly included in the consortium. Where possible, KERs will be published on the project website and EC's Horizon Results Platform, outlining their Pathway to Impact to facilitate further development and exploitation.

The KMKT methodology consists of the following three overall phases and is further described in detail below:

- Collect and Understand

- Validate and Analyse
- Transfer and Exploit

5.2 Knowledge Management and Knowledge Transfer (KMKT)

This section of the PDEC outlines the stepwise process, which will be carried out within NETTAG+ Task 5.2, and Task 5.4. This methodology will see KOs identified, collected, reviewed, and prioritised to project KERs with developed KTPs. The figure below outlines an example of a full Pathway to Impact. The following subsections will refer to Figure 1. to demonstrate how each step contributes to the development of this.

Figure 1: NETTAG+ Knowledge Transfer Methodology

5.2.1 Collect & Understand

Phase 1: Capturing of KOs in an internal Project Output Impact Plan Template.

Effective KT relies on careful identification and description of KOs to ensure that all key information is provided which will result in effective transfer (Figure 2). Quality control measures will be performed, to ensure that the project output(s) can be clearly understood by others who may not be experts in the relevant disciplines. Each project participant will treat information from other participants as confidential unless otherwise stated and not disclose it to other parties unless the information is publicly available. It is important for all project participants to note that project outputs are not only the final results of research, but they can also be part of the methodology to obtain the final result, which could be an innovation for a research area or process.

Phase one aims to understand the positioning of a project output to be able to carry out impactful KT activities. It intends to help clarify how the project output could be beneficial to different target and end users. This step identifies potential applications, target and end users and the eventual impact of a project output. This information will also inform the development of Knowledge Output Pathways (KOPs) of KOs that progress to being a KER having been assessed as having high potential application and impact.

Figure 2: NETTAG+ Knowledge Transfer Methodology: Collect and Understand

It should be noted that KOs/KERs, especially those collected early in the project, are likely to continue to develop over the course of NETTAG+. Collected knowledge will be periodically reviewed by ERINN, the Innovation Board and participants asked to provide updates if applicable. As the Knowledge Transfer Impact Plan Template will be available on the [NETTAG+ Google Drive](#), participants will be able to advise ERINN if a given KO/KER needs to be updated.

PROTOCOL – Collect & Understand

1. ERINN sends the KO Collection Template to NETTAG+ Task Leaders, who will be requested to complete it for any new, innovative result produced so far in the project.
 - If the Task Leader thinks another project participant in this Task is better placed to provide the requested information, then they should send it on to the relevant person(s).
2. For each identified KO, all fields of the Template should be completed. Explanations are provided under each question.
3. Completed Templates should be sent to ERINN.
4. In order to carry out first validation, ERINN may request to have further discussion (call or video conferencing) with the KO owner to discuss it in more detail.
5. First validation of the KO will be carried out by ERINN, whereby:
 - any typographical/editing errors will be corrected;
 - it will be determined if the short title of the KO(s) is sufficiently informative;
 - it will be established if the knowledge description of the KO(s) is sufficiently comprehensive to adequately understand the nature of the KO and to determine its possible applications;
 - potential end-users of the KO will be identified and listed, as well as their potential applications;
 - it will be clarified if the KO(s) is publicly available or is subject to IPR protection, which would have an effect on transfer potential; and
 - if deemed necessary, ERINN will contact the KO author(s) to discuss the KO and identify if there is anything missing or unclear.

5.2.2 Analyse & Validate

Phase 2: The collected project outputs are reviewed and assessed for potential application and impact.

Following up from the previous step, project outputs go through a Due Diligence process, whereby a more thorough examination and evaluation of the output and its applicability and readiness for transfer will be investigated (Figure 3). Due Diligence will be undertaken so that any factors that could affect the transfer potential (confidentiality, competition, IPR) of the output and ultimately the uptake and impact of the knowledge can be identified. Following Due Diligence, outputs will be prioritised and those with potential to have impact will go through to the next step. An essential step in the NETTAG+ KMKT methodology is the identification of output applications, potential impact and respective end users (e.g., applications could be in various areas and sectors not just the one in the research area of the project) for each output which has been assessed as having high potential application and impact.

Important aspects are prioritisation of potentially high-impact outputs and profiling target and end users to gain valuable data to inform successful Impact Plans. This is not a ranking of their importance but rather a method to help NETTAG+ identify where to focus transfer and exploitation efforts. For those prioritised, the expert groups will attempt to identify potential target users whose application of the knowledge would be of benefit in transferring it towards its eventual impact.

Those outputs that are validated and deemed to be of priority for the project will be re-labelled as **Key Exploitable Results (KERs)** and progressed to the third phase. Any output that is not made a KER will continue to be periodically reviewed and any remaining at the end of the project will still be captured as evidence of project results for final reporting. The identification of target users in the analysis stage is critical to laying the groundwork for transfer and exploitation plans in the third phase. The exercises in this phase may also serve to identify potential stakeholders that are worth connecting with, even in cases where the knowledge may not yet be ready for transfer.

Figure 3: NETTAG+ Knowledge Transfer Methodology: Analyse and Validate

PROTOCOL – Knowledge Analysis

At periodic intervals, ERINN will organise “expert analysis meetings” together with the Innovation Board.

The frequency and makeup of these meetings will be determined in collaboration with the Project Coordinator as well as based on the current status of knowledge collection and management in the project.

The expert analysis meetings will carry out a thorough examination and evaluation of the outputs (collected so far) and their applicability and readiness for transfer. Particular attention will be paid to:

- *Identification of all likely target- and end-users. We encourage project participants to be as specific as possible and innovative when determining potential end users.*
- *It is important to consider the following when profiling target- and end-users:*
 1. *Understand the user’s mandate or responsibilities;*
 2. *Consider their background knowledge, attitude, and practice in relation to the issue;*
 3. *Understand their knowledge needs;*
 4. *Understand what and who may influence their decisions;*
 5. *Be aware of their preferred sources of information and knowledge.*
- *Identification of associated application and impact potential.*
- *Assess the Technology Readiness Level (TRL) that could inform the development of an appropriate output pathway to impact, where the output requires further research, validation or scale-up.*

Experts in these meetings will be asked to:

- *Confirm the accuracy and feasibility of transfer both within and beyond the project (but as a direct result of the project) for each presented output, to the best of their understanding.*
- *Assign to each output a ranking to determine whether it should be prioritised as a KER based on its current status.*
- *Discuss and identify potential target users to whom the knowledge should be transferred to progress it towards its eventual impact.*

After each expert analysis meeting, ERINN will revise the Impact Plan Template to identify any progression of knowledge (such as an output being changed to a KER). If any questions emerge from the expert analysis meeting, ERINN will reach out to the relevant output owners to attempt to provide an answer.

5.2.3 Transfer & Exploit

Phase 3: Carry out and report on KT activities; while measuring the impact of both the activity and the application of the Knowledge by the User(s).

For each KER, a Knowledge Transfer Plan (KTP)/Pathway to Impact Plan will be developed. Implementing an efficient KTP that is tailor-made to the needs and capacities of specific target and end users (profiled in phase 2) will

maximise the chance of successful transfer resulting in uptake and application. The key to success is achieved through fully understanding the target- and end-user, and developing the KTP around them. There are a number of steps included in the KTP, and there are different downstream routes to reach its eventual impact. KTPs are the accumulation of numerous KT activities as represented in Figure 4.

KTPs will ensure KERs go through a Due Diligence process, whereby a more thorough examination and evaluation of the KER and its applicability and readiness for transfer will be investigated. Due Diligence will be undertaken so that any factors that could affect the transfer potential (confidentiality, competition, IPR) of the KER and ultimately the uptake and impact of the knowledge can be identified. The individual project participant within NETTAG+ best positioned to conduct the transfer will be identified and this phase will attempt to clearly describe how the impact of NETTAG+' KERs will be measured.

The work carried out in this phase will not only be important for accurately reporting the full breadth of impact of the project to the EC, but it will also assist all participants in carrying out exploitation activities. Not every KER transfer plan will be able to be reasonably executed during the lifetime of the project but, by delivering clear plans, the KM methodology will help establish how exploitation actions within the project will feed into the overall impact of the project as a whole, and help achieve the societal goals of NETTAG+.

Figure 4: NETTAG+ Knowledge Transfer Methodology: Transfer and Exploit

PROTOCOL – Knowledge Transfer and Exploitation

For any knowledge that has been determined to be a KER:

1. ERINN will collaborate with the Innovation Board, and the owner(s) of a KER to develop a Knowledge Transfer Plan (KTP)/Pathway to Impact for each KER. In particular, this effort will focus on the following considerations regarding the first target user(s) in the plan:
 - a) Building on the impact potential identified in the validation and analysis step, ensure that a concise and compelling narrative for the opportunity/business case is developed.
 - b) The technical level of the target user; the depth of information needed; and the style of language most effective for communicating with them.
 - c) The background knowledge of the target user.

- d) *Any preconceived ideas that the target user may have relating to the area of interest.*
- e) *Ways in which to relate the knowledge to examples with which the target user is familiar, or ones they can easily envisage.*
- f) *The level of evidence or validation that the target user requires.*

2. *ERINN will be responsible for drafting these plans, which will then be provided to the Project Coordinator and generating project participant(s).*
3. *Once a KTP has been drafted and reviewed, it will be opened up for feedback from the Innovation Board.*
4. *ERINN will work with all relevant project participants to assist where possible in the translation of KTPs into exploitation activities. The nature of these exploitation activities will be highly dependent on the KER, the target user, the transferring participant, the timeline, resources available, foreseen activities in the DoA, and other variable considerations. The exploitation activities themselves may be carried out within a range of externally focused tasks.*

5.3 Cost-Benefit Analysis

As part of work package 5 (T5.3), the cost-effectiveness of solutions developed to reduce marine litter will be assessed by the development of a cost-benefit analysis. Both the direct economic impact of NETTAG+ solutions (on energy use, raw materials, fishing effort, fishing operations, catch, and profitability) and revenues will be considered.

The potential redistribution of the estimated costs and revenues between innovative solutions (and fishers) will be also estimated, including a trade-offs analysis under different fisheries incentives and scenarios. The results of the cost-benefit output and trade-offs analysis will be made available to a selection of policy-makers and representatives of the fishing industry to allow them to identify strategies to improve fisheries management at the best cost-benefit when adopting our portfolio of innovative solutions.

6. Dissemination and Communication Resources

All NETTAG+ project participants will dedicate time to perform communication and dissemination activities and will be encouraged to engage in a two-way exchange with the public at large, and where possible the media, with the aim to show how EU research and innovation funding has a positive impact on society. Through its communication activities, NETTAG+ will demonstrate why working together in a European consortium is important in addressing a challenge that affects society.

To facilitate communication and dissemination throughout the project, a portfolio of promotional project material has been developed by CIIMAR under T6.1 in collaboration with WWF Med.

6.1 Promotional Materials

6.1.1 Logo and Brand

A specific project logo has been developed to visually represent the project. The project logo is an integral part of the brand as it is and will be included in all project's promotional materials both print and online. The NETTAG+ project logo is available in various versions. The different versions along with a Word and Power Point template can be found on the project's [Google Drive](#).

Figure 1: NETTAG+ Logo

PROTOCOL – Utilising NETTAG+ Branding alongside other Institutional Branding

While it is preferable that all participants use NETTAG+ branded resources when disseminating the project's results, we recognise that some institutions will require participants to use their own institutional branding for conferences and various presentations. To balance the interests of NETTAG +, and our contractual obligations to the EC, with various institutional requirements, we require the following requirements to be included at minimum:

- *The NETTAG+ logo must be included on at least the Title Page and Conclusion/Thank You slide, however usage on all slides would be preferred.*
- *The EU emblem and funding acknowledgement (GA Article 17) must always be visibly present on either the first or the last slide.*

6.1.2 Project Dissemination Templates

NETTAG+ PowerPoint and Poster Presentation Templates have been developed to use at internal and external events when presenting the NETTAG+ project. Additional assets such as Flyers/Factsheets, the Roll-Up Banner,

Infographics and Videos (in English and other languages as Portuguese, Spanish; Italian, Croatian and Maltese) will be developed over the course of the project and can be downloaded from the project [Google Drive](#) and requested from CIIMAR (contact: ssramos@ciimar.up.pt; calmeida@ciimar.up.pt; nettag@ciimar.up.pt).

PROTOCOL – Dissemination Templates

Project participants should use the NETTAG+ Dissemination Templates when promoting the project's objectives or presenting project results.

Download the Template from the [project Google Drive](#) and or request from CIIMAR (contact: ssramos@ciimar.up.pt; calmeida@ciimar.up.pt; nettag@ciimar.up.pt).

- *When using the PowerPoint Presentation Template, choose to insert “new slide” and pick your preferred content template.*
- *Respect all of the Templates’ format (background, font and layout).*
- *Always ensure that the correct EU Emblem, EU and non-EU funding logos and acknowledgements are present on any NETTAG+ presentations, deliverables and reports etc.*

6.1.3 Flyer/Factsheet

A promotional flyer presenting the NETTAG+ project, objectives and expected results will be developed in the 1st phase of the project for general communications but more importantly for 1) WP2 (D2.1) specifically aimed at fishers using simple, non-scientific language (in English, Portuguese, Spanish, Italian and Croatian). The flyers/factsheets can be shared digitally and distributed at relevant events. They will be available as a download on the NETTAG+ website and the project [Google Drive](#) or upon request to CIIMAR (ssramos@ciimar.up.pt; calmeida@ciimar.up.pt). Project participants are encouraged to distribute the flyer through their networks and at relevant events. If participants wish to have the flyer available in another language, they should follow the protocol outlined below.

PROTOCOL – Factsheet Translation

- *Contact CIIMAR (contact person: ssramos@ciimar.up.pt; calmeida@ciimar.up.pt; nettag@ciimar.up.pt) requesting the original factsheet template with English text.*
- *CIIMAR supplies the template with the original text in English to requesting project participant.*
- *Project participant translates the text (as laid out in the template) into their language.*
- *Project participant then sends the translated text back to CIIMAR.*
- *CIIMAR applies the translated text to the flyer template and publishes the new version of the flyer, after validation and sign-off from the project participant responsible for the translation.*

6.1.4 Roll-Up Banner

A NETTAG+ Roll-up Banner will be designed and developed for use at internal and external events to raise awareness about the project, for example at exhibition booths or for fishers awareness activities (D2.1). The banner content will be sent to the different project partners for translation into the required languages (Italian, Portuguese, Maltese, Spanish, Croatian). Once developed, the banner can be found on the NETTAG+ website, project [Google Drive](#) or it can be requested from CIIMAR (ssramos@ciimar.up.pt; calmeida@ciimar.up.pt) in the different languages.

PROTOCOL – Roll-up Banner Printing

- *Project participants can make use of the NETTAG+ Pull-up Banner at internal and external events to raise awareness about the project.*
- *The template is designed to print as a standard pull-up banner measuring 200cm x 80 cm however, if a partner requires different dimensions, CIIMAR will endeavour to adjust the banner template to the partner's needs.*
- *Please print the pull-up banner in full colour, making no adjustments to the colour settings.*
- *The pull-up banner can be found on the NETTAG+ website, project Google Drive, or it can be requested from CIIMAR (ssramos@ciimar.up.pt; calmeida@ciimar.up.pt) for any queries around dimensions, printing and material requirements.*

6.1.5 Website

The project website will be developed following the EU's best practice guidelines for project websites. The website will be fully compliant with the General Data Protection Regulation (EU 2016/679, GDPR) by incorporating a privacy statement and cookie bar informing website visitors about what NETTAG+ does with any personal data gathered. Google Analytics is used to track traffic and monitor the use of the website, which will be used to inform Continuous Reporting. To ensure the successful promotion of the project and to sustain the interest of the target audience and attract new users, the website's content will be maintained, continuously updated and populated with new information throughout the project's lifetime. The website will remain live for five years after the end of the project, serving as a valuable public resource of research information on the subject and promoting the outputs of this publicly funded research.

PROTOCOL – Website Content: Requests for posting and uploading

- *CIIMAR together with WWF will manage the NETTAG+ website and will be updating it on a regular basis.*
- *Project participants who might have feedback on the site or wish to upload materials, news or events to the website (e.g., calendar) should contact CIIMAR (ssramos@ciimar.up.pt; calmeida@ciimar.up.pt).*

- *Project participants are encouraged to include a link to the NETTAG+ website on their own institution websites (see section 6.1.6).*

6.1.6 Social Media

Social media is an integral part of the NETTAG+ communication strategy. The project results and outputs will be actively disseminated through the NETTAG+ social media channels including [Facebook](#), [Twitter](#), and [Instagram](#) (managed by CIIMAR and WWF). Stakeholders are encouraged to follow NETTAG+ on social media. A dedicated #hashtag (#NETTAG) might also be created to increase monitoring.

As with other means of communication, attention should be paid to the content being shared on social media. The consortium should determine which information to keep confidential and which to publish, where and to what extent. If you have questions about what is appropriate, please contact CIIMAR (ssramos@ciimar.up.pt; calmeida@ciimar.up.pt) or WWF Med (scampogianni@wwfmedpo.org).

In order for NETTAG+ to create an engaging and thriving online community, it will be necessary to effectively manage potential risks. The following are guidelines for all participants who participate in social media and apply whether participants are posting to the NETTAG+ accounts, their own accounts or commenting on other accounts.

PROTOCOL – NETTAG+ Internal Code of Social Media Conduct

Participants should try to contribute to social media channels where possible. Guidance can be requested from WWFMed.

General Rules

- *Ensure the content is yours to share (research or opinions) or acknowledge the source accordingly.*
- *Ensure there are no IP issues.*
- *Use appropriate tags and hashtags to acknowledge funding.*
- *If you communicate publicly about NETTAG+ or NETTAG+ -related matters, you must disclose your role within the project.*
- *Do not use offensive language, argumentative or illegal content, etc.*
- *Be professional, use good judgement and be accurate and honest in your communications; unprofessional language or behaviour reflect poorly on the project, and may result in liability.*
- *Unless approved by the coordinator CIIMAR, your social media name, handle and URL should not include NETTAG+ project's name or logo.*
- *Be mindful around controversial subjects, where emotions may run high e.g., politics. It is important to show respect for others' opinions.*

X (former twitter)

Participants wishing to communicate via the NETTAG+ Twitter accounts have the following options:

- Send a suggested post message (280 characters max) to WWFMed (scampogianni@wwfmedpo.org) who can post from the NETTAG+ account on your behalf. Ideally, include an image or short video to make it more visually appealing.
- Post from your own X (former Twitter) account and refer to NETTAG+ by tagging @NetTagProject in the text or image; WWF will always aim to retweet/share such posts.
- Retweet/share NETTAG+ posts through your personal and institutional social media accounts.

Tips

- Social media is becoming increasingly visual — post pictures, videos, GIFs or data visualisations.
- Engage with your audience using replies, retweets/shares or tags.
- Ask questions instead of making statements to drive conversation.
- Leverage existing social media presence e.g., the host institution, researchers, team members or other relevant organisations, and tag and follow relevant accounts, particularly EC accounts (i.e. @HorizonEU, @EUScienceInnov, @EUGreenResearch)
- Follow the news and use trending hashtags where appropriate.
- Content could include the announcement of milestones, results, scientific publications, press releases, newsletters, etc. or when the project is featured at a conference or event.

6.1.7 Press Releases

At least 10 press releases will be issued to appropriate media outlets (trade press, newspapers) to ensure that industry, communities, civil society, policymakers, and the wider public are aware of the project, its objectives and its later outcomes. The strategy is intended to ensure that there is media coverage at local, national, regional, European and international levels. CIIMAR and WWF will share project news through internal (consortium mailing list, stakeholder database and project participant networks) and external (press releases, social media, etc.) channels, which ensures a broad awareness of the project across the spectrum of relevant stakeholders. Project participants are encouraged to publish articles and press releases at regional, national, and international levels, making use of their own communication networks and channels. CIIMAR and WWFMed can provide some support to project participants in these activities (e.g. checking media release).

PROTOCOL – Press Releases

- Project participants should notify CIIMAR and WWFMed if there is news suitable for an official project press release:
- CIIMAR and WWFMed will develop a draft and seek approval from the NETTAG+ Coordination team.
- Once approved, press releases will be disseminated using appropriate channels.
- They will be uploaded to the project website and all project participants are encouraged to distribute at national or regional level.
- Where necessary the project participants can adapt the press releases to customise them to their audience and if needed translate the articles.

NOTE: Project participants may also initiate the writing of press releases (e.g., local, national). CIIMAR and WWFMed can then support writing and editing if required. Participants are asked to provide a short summary in English if the original communication is in another language. Participants who publish any article/press release at a regional or national level must send a copy to CIIMAR and WWFMed and where possible provide metrics (e.g. press coverage, social media monitoring) to demonstrate uptake by other news channels/readership.

6.1.8 Video

At least 6 professional videos and at least 5 shorter media clips will be developed for participants to disseminate and promote the NETTAG+ project and its outcomes. NETTAG+ professional videos will be developed for project participants to disseminate and promote the NETTAG+ project at events and on social media. The videos will showcase the project to key stakeholders and the general public, explaining the main issues the project is tackling, the role of fishers as guardians of the sea and the solutions and benefits the project will deliver to local communities and for ocean's health. All videos – independently of the language spoken by its characters - will be provided with English subtitles (and if possible other relevant languages) to encourage widespread distribution by all participants in their channels and at relevant events.

6.1.9 Other Resources and Tools

As the project progresses infographics, social media visuals and videos, etc. will be created to present the project activities in an attractive and creative way. These resources and tools will be uploaded to the NETTAG+ website under a dedicated section and participants will be encouraged to share them through their channels. Other promotional material can be developed as required. Please contact CIIMAR (ssramos@ciimar.up.pt, calmeida@ciimar.up.pt; nettag@ciimar.up.pt) or WWF Med (scampogianni@wwfmedpo.org) with any other ideas for promotional material to support your communication and dissemination activities.

7. Dissemination and Communication Activities

The purpose of NETTAG+ dissemination and communication activities is to make the project, its activities and key results and benefits known to key stakeholders and the general public. All NETTAG+ participants will perform dissemination and communication activities (in line with the planned effort) and will be encouraged to reach and engage the wider public (especially their members and followers), and where possible the media, with the aim to show how EU research and innovation funding provide an added value to society and for long-term sustainability.

Through its dissemination and communication activities, NETTAG+ will demonstrate why working together in a European consortium is important in addressing a challenge that affects all communities.

7.1 PDEC Tools, Channels and Target Groups

As the project progresses, it will be critical to ensure that the project outcomes are effectively and efficiently transferred to key users from various sectors (industry, fisheries, policy, and research). Each targeted audience will be reached using appropriate messages, means, and style. In order to effectively promote and spread awareness about the NETTAG+ approach and results, the following communication tools and activities (Table 2) will be designed and implemented by the consortium and coordinated and monitored by WP6.

Table 2. NETTAG+ PDEC tools, channels and target groups (high level)

NETTAG+ Communication and Dissemination tools & channels	Industry	Scientists	Policy actors	Society
Project website Target: online for at least another 5 years after project end. Regular updates. >10,000 visits over the project duration, >250 directly signed up to 'subscribe to news' through the website.	✓	✓	✓	✓
Press releases & Promotional articles Target: at least 10 original press-releases or promotional articles published, leading to further publication of at least 25 articles in websites, the press, and specialised publications.	✓	✓	✓	✓
Videos Target: At least 6 professional videos and at least 5 shorter media clips are expected to be viewed by more than 10,000 people in total.	✓	✓	✓	✓
Social media strategy Target: social media presence latest from M3 and for the full duration of the project, with Twitter; LinkedIn; Facebook; Instagram and other social media activity and targeted promotional campaigns (for promoting specific topics) expecting to reach more than 50,000 people.	✓	✓	✓	✓
Participation in relevant virtual and physical events Target: NETTAG+ will be represented in the major relevant international (research, policy and industry) events over the full duration of the project (e.g. EU Maritime Day; Business2Sea; EU Sustainable blue economy brokerage event on fishery; Mediterranean UNEP/MAP events; etc).	✓	✓	✓	

<p>Project network and events Target: active cooperation with the other projects selected under this call topic and complementary projects particularly those funded under Mission Ocean will be established, e.g. common events, exchange of information, collaboration in the Horizon Booster programme, etc.</p>	✓	✓	✓	
<p>Outreach activities Target: all partners aim to participate in local science outreach events, e.g. European Researchers Night; national clean-up events; partners outreach events (e.g. CIIMAR scientific disseminations centres; open days; WWF marine litter events; INESC TEC open days; USC outreach activities; etc)</p>			✓	✓
<p>Open access scientific publications (in high impact peer-reviewed journals), review articles and editorials Target: Between 8-10 publications (e.g. Frontiers in Marine Science; Marine Policy; Marine Pollution Bulletin; IEEE, Sustainability; ICES Journal of Marine Science, and repositories like EMODnet; MedSeaLitter; Ocean Best Practices, Litterbase and JRC publications repository, etc.).</p>	✓	✓	✓	

7.2 External Events

All project participants are committed to engage the public in their research activities and results and take advantage of the potential for public interest that NETTAG+ generates. Project participants are encouraged to develop dissemination activities that are appropriate for their respective contributions. WWFMed can provide guidance and some support to identify potential communication opportunities and results. Examples include live broadcasts, news stories, institute open days, etc.

The project results will also be presented as oral presentations, posters, etc. at major international meetings and conferences of relevance to NETTAG+. Conferences, seminars, workshops, and other meetings are very useful fora to consult with our target audiences in a face-to-face way and to address and encourage solutions on issues relevant to the work done in the project. International and sector-relevant conferences, meetings, etc. will be frequently attended to communicate the results of the project to the maximum number of persons. See the protocol for public outreach activities below.

Table 3 shows a list of potential events that may be of interest to NETTAG+ participants or stakeholders. These events will be added to the project website.

Table 3. Relevant events for NETTAG+ consortium and stakeholders

Event	Location	Date
UN Ocean Decade Event	Barcelona	April 2024
Mission Ocean Forums	Europe	Yearly in February
European Maritime Day	Europe	Yearly in May
ICMPSS - International Conference on Microplastics and Plastic Pollution Studies	London	Yearly in August
ICES - Arctic Plastics 2023	Reykjavik, Iceland	22-23 November 2023
BANOS Arena Stakeholder Forum	Gothenburg, Sweden	November 14-17 th 2023
EAFP – European Association of Fish Pathologists e.V.	Europe	Every two years
ISAAH – American Fisheries Society	North America/Global	Every four years
EU Beach Clean Up event		Yearly in September

PROTOCOL – Public Outreach Activities: Internal and External Events

Project participants should notify CIIMAR and WWFMed if there is news suitable for official project outreach activities:

- *Project participants should inform the Project Coordinator and WWFMed of their planned outreach activities so they can be promoted.*
- *Project participants should inform other participants about the event via email. If the planned outreach activity involves the dissemination of NETTAG+ results, the pre-dissemination requirements of the prior notice protocol and the IP assessment form must be carried out (see section 3.1).*
- *All public engagement and outreach activities must be reported during (internal and external) reporting periods.*
- *WWFMed and CIIMAR will include events on the NETTAG+ website.*
- *WWFMed will update the EC Portal on all Dissemination Activities.*

7.3 Scientific Publications – Relevant Journals

The consortium expects to publish 8-10 high-impact articles, submitted to pre-print servers prior to peer-reviewed OA journals. In total the consortium expects to publish at least 25 OA articles over the full duration of the project. NETTAG+ scientific publications will be published in gold OA (budget included) journals and adhere to the FAIR principles for research outputs, e.g. OA data deposition.

Participating in open peer review - Partners will be encouraged to use platforms, such as Open Research Europe, which provides avenues to publish in open access, boost research credibility, enhance the visibility of the work, and to develop a better understanding in the field. In addition, partners will be asked to share work where possible, including non-traditional article types e.g. data notes, study protocols, and systematic reviews. Open Science practices will be integrated as rules and recommended protocols into the NETTAG+ DMP.

8. PDEC Monitoring and Evaluation

The PDEC functions as an operation manual and will be updated throughout the project. WP5 leader ERINN will continue to review and amend the PDEC in line with the latest DEC activities and project results. As part of the revision process, each subsequent version of this deliverable will be validated by the consortium. Furthermore, the project coordinator (CIIMAR) and project participants will also review the PDEC at each review stage and provide recommendations. The current version will function as the operational manual and will be revised as part of D5.5 – Roadmap (M36).

9. Project participants involved in the work

All project participants are expected to carry out dissemination and exploitation activities as well as communication activities. WWFMed and ERINN will provide coordination and support to these activities.

Appendix

Annex 1 – Glossary

“**Access rights**” are the rights to use results or background related to the project, as set out in the Grant Agreement

(<https://ec.europa.eu/info/fundingtenders/opportunities/portal/screen/support/glossary>).

“**Background**” Any data, know-how and/or information, whatever its form or nature (tangible or intangible) – including any rights such as intellectual property rights – which are needed to carry out the project or exploit its results. (<https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/support/glossary>) .

“**Dissemination**” means the public disclosure of the results by any appropriate means (other than resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including by scientific publications in any medium. (https://www.iprhelphdesk.eu/sites/default/files/newsdocuments/FS-Plan-for-the-exploitation-and-dissemination-of-results_1.pdf)

“**End Users**” are last Target User identified on the *Knowledge Output Pathway*, i.e. individual(s) who will apply the *Knowledge Output* at the end of the *Knowledge Output Pathway*. Once they apply the KO, Eventual Impact is reached. The Knowledge Output may have undergone several revisions/adaptations through the value chain before reaching/being relevant to the needs of the end-user. Definition according to COLUMBUS (Horizon 2020 project: 652690).

“**Exploitation**” means the use of results in further research activities other than those covered by the action concerned, or in developing, creating and marketing a product or process, or in creating and providing a service, or in standardisation activities. (https://www.iprhelphdesk.eu/sites/default/files/newsdocuments/FS-Plan-for-the-exploitation-and-dissemination-of-results_1.pdf)

“**Eventual Impact**” the ultimate end benefit of the application of the *Knowledge Output*, and its influence/effect once taken up and applied by the target community. It is defined as an enhanced situation that is contributing to a need (political, industrial, scientific or societal). Definition according to COLUMBUS (Horizon 2020 project: 652690).

“**Knowledge Management**” is the process of identifying, capturing, analysing, organising, and storing knowledge to ensure its availability and ability to be transferred effectively to specific users. It comprises a range of practices used by organisations to identify, create, represent, and distribute knowledge for reuse, awareness and learning. Definition according to MarineTT (FP7 project number 244164); COLUMBUS (Horizon 2020 project: 652690).

“Knowledge Outputs” are units of knowledge or learning generated by or through research activity. They are not limited to de-novo or pioneering discoveries but may also include new methodologies/processes, adaptations, insights, alternative applications of prior know-how/ knowledge. Definition according to COLUMBUS (Horizon 2020 project: 652690).

“Knowledge Output Pathway” can be a single step or a series of steps required to carry a Knowledge Output to its Eventual Impact. Where there are a series of steps, it will include detailed mapping of the steps, the users involved at each step and their predicted role in the pathway to Eventual Impact. Definition according to COLUMBUS (Horizon 2020 project: 652690).

“Knowledge Transfer” is the term for the overall process of moving knowledge between knowledge sources to targeted potential users of knowledge. Knowledge Transfer consists of a range of activities which aim to capture, organise, assess and transmit knowledge, skills and competence from those who generate them to those who will utilise them. Definition according to COLUMBUS (Horizon 2020 project: 652690).

“Target User” is the individual(s) who you have identified in your Knowledge Output Pathway to whom a Knowledge Output will be transferred. They are not necessarily the end-user or participant of the KO; rather they can be the steppingstone needed for a KO to progress towards an *Eventual Impact*. More than one Target User can be part of one KOP. Definition according to COLUMBUS (Horizon 2020 project: 652690).

Annex 2 – IP Assessment Form

Table 4. IP Assessment Form for screening of dissemination and communication activities to ensure protection of results. Cells in teal to be filled by author, cells in turquoise to be filled by WP5 lead ERINN.

IP Assessment Prior to Dissemination	Description / Comments
Title of the Dissemination or Communication Activity	
<p>Type of Dissemination or Communication activities, including details on names, dates, places, etc.</p> <p><i>Scientific Publications: Article in Journal; Publication in Conference proceedings/ Workshop; Book/ Monograph; Chapter in a Book; Thesis/ Dissertation; Other</i></p> <p><i>Dissemination activities: Organisation of Conferences, Education and training events, Meetings, Clustering activities, Collaboration with EU-funded projects, Other scientific collaboration, Other.</i></p> <p><i>Communication activities/channels: Website, Social media, Print materials (brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners etc), Press release, Media article, Newsletter, Interview, Video, TV/Radio campaign, Event (conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate, round table, group discussion etc), Exhibition, Other</i></p>	
Where to find it (if it is/will be published)?	
<p>Have all contributors to the Dissemination or Communication Activity been included in the author list where relevant, or are otherwise properly acknowledged?</p> <p><i>Include the names of the authors here</i></p>	

<p>Do all authors agree on this Dissemination or Communication activity?</p> <p><i>Declaration of the main/ corresponding author. Please state your agreement on the right.</i></p>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Q1: Have other institutions been involved in this Dissemination or Communication Activity? • Q2: If yes, have all involved institutions taken care of ownership issues by filling out this IP form? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Answer to Q1: • Answer to Q2:
<p>Is appropriate acknowledgment to EU included?</p> <p><i>Note: always include the statement indicated in the NETTAG+ Brand Guidelines into any NETTAG+ Dissemination or Communication Activity.</i></p> <p><i>If possible, also include the EU emblem</i></p>	
<p>Is acknowledgment to other funding sources included if relevant?</p> <p><i>Note: UK partners are funded by their own national resources. If the activity includes partners from these countries, make sure to additionally include the correct acknowledgment.</i></p>	
<p>Which part of the NETTAG+ project does the Dissemination or Communication Activity correspond with?</p> <p><i>Include WP number and, if possible, tasks numbers</i></p>	
<p>Does the Dissemination or Communication Activity include work originating also from non- NETTAG+ work, e.g., from other EU or nationally funded projects?</p> <p><i>Include name/code (Grant Agreement number) of the project</i></p>	

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Q1: Is the result you are aiming to disseminate considered to be commercially/ industrially exploitable? • Q2: If yes, have you protected the result prior to dissemination, please give details? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Answer to Q1: • Answer to Q2:
<p>Do you, as a reviewer, consider the result that is aimed to be disseminated here, to be commercially/ industrially exploitable? Please give clarifications.</p>	
<p>Does the information contain any personal data?</p> <p>If yes, has permission been obtained for the public use of such data? If yes, please include this.</p>	
<p>Do all authors agree on the Dissemination or Communication Activity being disclosed through the NETTAG+ channels (e.g., project website) once accepted/ presented?</p> <p><i>A declaration of the main/ corresponding author indicates that all participants agree</i></p>	
<p>Which stakeholders could be interested in knowing about the results and the conclusions of your Dissemination or Communication Activity?</p> <p><i>Choose the relevant target group(s) among:</i></p> <p>A) Industry B) Policy/ decision-makers C) Scientists D) Consumers/ general public E) Other stakeholders (please specify)</p> <p><i>Please specify as detailed as possible</i></p>	
<p>Date of submission to WP5 Lead ERINN</p>	

Recommendations:

<p>WP5 lead ERINN recommendation (to publish or protect)</p>	
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Authorisations:

<p>Main author publication</p>	<p>WP6 lead ERINN</p>
<p>Date: Signature:</p>	<p>Date: Signature:</p>

